

MELODY BOUNCE: MOBILE RHYTHMIC INTERACTION FOR CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an audio-based game for mobile devices, designed to develop rhythmical and timing abilities in elementary-school-aged children. Developing such skills is believed to be very important for social interaction and interpersonal coordination. Moreover, increasing evidence suggests that rhythmicity has a direct influence on other cognitive abilities such as motor coordination and sustaining attention. The game makes exclusive use of motion-based input and non-verbal audio feedback, being therefore equally enjoyable by children which might speak different languages and might or might not have visual impairments. The game logic is inherently collaborative and multiplayer, in order to promote a sense of inclusion of the child among the group of players. The game design is heavily inspired by observations of children's activities in schools, which are usually characterized by strong rhythmic patterns.

1. INTRODUCTION

Music plays a fundamental role in the life of every human being. Like verbal and visual languages, the art of organizing sounds has developed in every part of the world. There is wide agreement among music theorists and psychologists that our understanding of music is for the most part pre-cultural and wired in the structure of our auditory perceptual grouping [1].

Musical abilities are already present in very young children: even in the pre-kindergarten years children love to sing, play instruments, dance and listen to music [2]. As they grow up songs, rhymes and musical games become a crucial part of their social interactions and learning, with other children as well as with adults. Elementary-school-aged children eagerly sing full-voice songs learnt by their peers, by adults or through the media. They use musical utterances to make their playing activity more immersive and convincing, support the coordination of their movements with rhythmic chants or counting out loud. Those behaviors are found not only in organized games but also during free play, classroom work and any other kind of activity [3].

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Figure 1. Children playing a rhythmic chant in the playground. Image courtesy: Mary Ann Moss

The value of these musical expressions often lays more in the social process they trigger rather than in the produced sound itself. To use the words of Christopher Small the act of *musicking* [4], namely the participation in a music-making activity in any capacity (for example by performing, listening, practicing, composing, or dancing), helps to create meaningful relations among all the participants. A performance which creates the right connections and fulfills the expectation of everyone involved, can be a very powerful framework to embed other activities such as teaching concepts belonging to different subjects, promoting positive social behaviors among the group, maintaining children physically and mentally engaged or asking for their attention.

Observing musical activities made by children, one of the most striking aspects is that they are characterized by very strong rhythmical patterns. Moreover, the rhythm is imposed not only through the production of sounds but also with the physical movement of the whole body. Starting from the 1920s, musical educators such as Dalcroze [5] and Orff [6] became aware of this, and started to base their teaching methods on these particular features of children play. Nevertheless, the importance of developing a good sense of rhythm and timing goes well beyond the context of playing games or music: work from Bernieri and Rosenthal shows how being rhythmically “in tune” with other people improves social relationships and what they call *interpersonal coordination* [7]. There is also evidence that rhythmicity directly influences other cognitive abilities like

sustaining attention, controlling impulsivity and coordinating motion [8].

It is important to remember that in addition to actual world activities, like running in the playground or playing a musical instrument, today's children are getting more and more engaged with activities happening inside the digital world. A 2011 survey about 0 to 8-year-old children's media use in America indicates that while TV continues to be by far the most consumed medium by that age group, more than a quarter of screen time is spent on digital devices. At least half of all children now have access to a mobile device at home, and more than a quarter of all parents have downloaded *apps* for their children to use [9]. The motion-sensing and multimodal feedback capabilities offered by smartphones and tablet PCs open the possibility to develop digital games featuring a rich musical rhythmic interaction, which is so favored by children during their physical world activities.

2. RELATED WORK

From a Human Computer Interaction (HCI) perspective, rhythmical aspects and sound design for children are both relatively unexplored fields. In the work of Jylhä and Erkut [10], the potential of rhythmic interaction is investigated through the design of an application which uses rhythmical patterns generated by hand clapping to manipulate musical content. Their approach proves to be effective, especially in those cases where an eyes-free interaction is needed or desirable. Applications for mobile devices may fall in this category, because of the limited size of their display and because of the greater freedom of movement gained when performing motion-based gestures if the user is no more required to look at the screen.

The most promising efforts in sound design for children have probably been made in the context of audio-based games, namely computer games which rely on sound rather than on visual information as their primary feedback to the user. Eriksson and Gärdenfors [11] propose a set of guidelines for the design of computer games for visually impaired children, which they put into practice in the development of a collection of games for the Swedish Association of Talking Books and Braille. Even if not specifically addressed to children, research presented in [12] and [13] is interesting in that it investigates the use of non-verbal audio feedback in audio-based games. Avoiding spoken language allows the design of a game which is enjoyable by children who are not yet able to speak or which speak different languages.

The work of Michalowski et al. [14] concentrates on the relevance of rhythmic movements in general social interaction, through the design and implementation of a dancing robot for children. The system is capable to dance following a dominant rhythm, which can be extracted by the acoustic and visual information captured by its microphones and cameras. Observations of children's interactions with the robot at a public installation showed that when it was dancing in sync with the underlying music, users tended to spend more time with it and to behave themselves in a more rhythmically organized way.

Figure 2. The Whack-A-Mole arcade game

Digital systems focusing on rhythmic interaction are also being used for rehabilitation purposes. One example is the Interactive Metronome® [8], which combines motion sensing features, acoustic and visual feedbacks to provide a series of exercises designed to improve the timing abilities of the patients. The authors claim that training the sense of rhythm leads to appreciable improvements in many other skills like coordinating motion, sustaining attention, managing impulsivity and collaborating with others, and that patients suffering from disorders related to those skills (i.e. ADHD, dyslexia, autism and other similar conditions) benefit greatly from such a treatment.

3. GAME DESIGN

The work presented in this paper is a game which exploits rhythmic interaction to develop and improve children's musical abilities, sense of timing and social interactions. Particular efforts have been put in designing an experience which should be enjoyable per se but also suitable for basic musical education and ear training. To achieve this goals, design choices were driven by observing and trying to mimick the interactions that normally occur in self-organized playground games.

As already stated in section 1 sound production and rhythmic movement of the whole body are the most relevant aspects of such playground games, thus the decision to develop an application based on motion gestures as input and auditory feedback as output. This style of interaction seems to have great potentials in terms of ear training and

enhancement of one’s listening capabilities [15], enables accessibility to visual-impaired users [16] [17] and has relatively low requirements in terms of processing power compared to its visual-based counterparts [18] [19]. This last element makes audio-based games well suited for mobile or other embedded devices, which often have limited computing capabilities and very small displays.

Like children playground activities, the designed game needs to be played by multiple players at the same time. It should also engage children in a collaborative rather than competitive activity, in order to foster inclusion of every single member in the playing group and positive, constructive social connections. This is also one of the distinguishing features of the act of making music together: every single element contributes with his or her individual effort to build the common “voice” of the whole group.

The game logic needs to be simple enough to be immediately understandable and enjoyable by young children, yet provide for an engaging and amusing experience. In order to achieve that, we used the *Whac-A-Mole* arcade game (see Figure 2) as a source of inspiration. This all-time classic is around from the mid seventies, and since then has gathered a tremendous success in the physical as well as in the digital world. Lots of versions have been made, changing the subject to whack (moles, cartoon characters, celebrities and so on) or the “weapon” used to whack them (hammers, cakes, shotguns and much more). The notoriety of this game and the simplicity of its rules played a key role in the decision of using it as the starting point of our design.

The resulting game design is therefore an auditory variant of the *Whac-A-Mole* game for mobile devices. Children have to shake their devices whenever they hear a note coming from their speakers, and stay still when they hear notes coming from their neighbors. The goal is to “whack” as many notes as possible in sequence without mistakes in order to unfold the whole melody. Missed notes result in a failure sound and the restart of the melody from its beginning, while a full successful sequence triggers a high quality recorded version of the nursery rhyme as a reward sound.

4. IMPLEMENTATION

The game client is an app developed in Objective-C for iOS 4.3 or later, and communicates with a custom server developed in Python via text-based TCP messages. The client presents a minimal Graphical User Interface (GUI) (see Figure 3) consisting of two views: the main view is merely a wallpaper image occupying the whole screen, which serves mainly for aesthetic purposes and to give some visual feedback about the fact that the game is running. The settings view contains the controls to perform the match making: users can create a new game or join an already existing group. All in-game information is given uniquely by sound.

Gesture recognition is done processing raw data coming from the embedded accelerometer. When the sum of the magnitudes of the x , y , and z acceleration components raises above a certain threshold, a shake is detected. While

Figure 3. The Graphical User Interface of the game. Right side: the GUI, left side: the settings view.

the device keeps moving fast, no other gestures can be triggered. When the same quantity stated above goes under another threshold (lower than the previous one), quiet is detected and other gestures can be triggered again. Although iOS provides higher-level methods to detect device shakes, we decided not to use them in order to keep the system more flexible and to allow future detection of different kind of gestures (swings, rolls, thrusts and so on).

Musical notes are synthesized in real-time using the *libpd* framework [20]. This library enables the loading and processing of *PureData* patches inside the mobile application, providing a powerful, flexible and easy to program sound synthesis engine. Musical parameters like pitch, dynamics and timbre can be manipulated in different and creative ways, and other sound effects can be generated to reflect the performed gestures or just to add a funny, cartoonish touch to the game.

5. PRELIMINARY EVALUATION

The presented work is just in its preliminary steps and no extensive testing of the platform has been made yet. A preliminary evaluation was performed by presenting the game to First two four-year old girls and one six-year old boy and observing their behavior. Observations showed that the game was quite hard for them to play. The first prototype handled errors in a draconian way, making the melody stop and restart from the beginning as soon as a single note was missed. The fact they could never win the game was very frustrating for them, and after just a couple of minutes they got bored and stopped playing. Possible improvements might be allowing a greater number of errors before stopping the melody, or relaxing the time boundaries in which a note can be “hit”.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This paper presents the first steps towards the development of rhythmic based collaborative sonic interaction games for children, that use current mobile technologies. It is important for the technology to be meaningful as part of the game and enhance the gaming experience.

This can be achieved by adding further developments of the games will include the recognition of a greater number of gestures, which will then be used to drive the sound synthesis engine and manipulate notes and sound effects accordingly. Another interesting feature to is the possibility for teachers to add new melodies to the game, by extending the existing mobile application and/or through a web-based interface. Groups of children and teachers could sing and record their favorite tunes, then make them available in the game to be discovered and enjoyed by other groups of children and teachers all around the world.

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